

Alkali Oxodiperoxovanadate(V) Complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]^-$. First Isolation in the Solid State, Characterisation and Structural Assessment

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Alkali metal oxodiperoxovanadates(V), $\text{A}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$ ($\text{A}=\text{NH}_4$, Na or K), have been synthesised by the reaction of V_2O_5 with 30% hydrogen peroxide and the corresponding alkali hydroxide AOH, in the concentration ratio 1 : 41.8 : 5.3-6.6, followed by precipitation with ethanol. The compounds are yellow and diamagnetic, and their molar conductances in water at ambient temperature lie between 130 and 140 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The results of infrared and laser Raman spectroscopic studies suggest that the complex species $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]^-$, contains a terminally bonded V=O group, and that the peroxide (O_2^{2-}) ligand is bonded to the vanadium(V) centre in a triangular bidentate (C_{2v}) manner. The complex $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]^-$ ion may be a pentacoordinated monomer, however, a hexacoordinated structure through a weak $-\text{V}=\text{O} \dots \text{V}=\text{O} \dots \text{V}=\text{O} \dots$ interaction can not be ruled out. As an example of its reactivity, the potassium salt of the complex ion $\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$, has been shown to undergo facile reaction with KF, and 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy) to produce $\text{K}_2[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2\text{F}]$, and $\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{dipy})]$, respectively.

BECAUSE of the biochemical significance^{1,2}, and importance in the oxidation chemistry³⁻⁶ for the activation and transfer of oxygen to organic substrates of peroxo transition metal compounds that studies on peroxo-vanadium chemistry has emerged as one of the active areas of current research^{5,7-15}. The synthesis of well defined peroxo-vanadium compounds followed by the study of their different properties provide a means in understanding the chemistry of such compounds. It has been known that vanadium-hydrogen peroxide system gives different colour reactions under slightly varying pH of the reaction medium^{10,16,17} and it is believed that the yellow colour of vanadium(V)- H_2O_2 solution owes its origin to the formation of a diperoxovanadate(V) anion^{16,17}, $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]^-$. However, earlier attempts to obtain the complex in the solid state failed¹⁷. The triperoxovanadate(V) complex, $\text{A}[\text{V}(\text{O}_2)_3]$ ($\text{A}=\text{alkali metal}$), has been synthesised only very recently¹⁸. The present paper reports the first successful synthesis, characterisation and structural assessment of the yellow alkali oxodiperoxovanadates(V), $\text{A}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$ ($\text{A}=\text{NH}_4$, Na or K). Also reported are two reactions involving the potassium salt, $\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$, which highlight the scope for the use of these compounds in synthesis.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of reagent grade. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer. Raman spectral measurements were made on a SPEX Ramalog 1403 spectrometer. The 4800 Å laser line from the Spectra-Physics 165 argon laser was used as the excitation

source. The scattered light at 90° was detected with the help of a cooled RCA 31034 photomultiplier tube, followed by photon-count processing system. The sample was held either in a quartz capillary or in the form of a pressed pellet. The spectra were recorded at ambient temperatures. Molar conductance measurements were made using a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by the Gouy method, using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The pH was measured with a Systronics 335 digital pH meter.

Synthesis of alkali oxodiperoxovanadate(V), $\text{A}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$ ($\text{A}=\text{NH}_4$, Na or K): Powdered V_2O_5 and 30% hydrogen peroxide were mixed in the concentration ratio of $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 : \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ as 1 : 41.8 followed by the addition of alkali hydroxide, AOH, with slow stirring until V_2O_5 dissolved to produce a clear yellow solution with its pH lying between 7 and 8. While aqueous ammonia was added in the form of its concentrated solution (specific gravity 0.9), sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide was added in the solid form. The resulting solution was cooled in an ice-water bath for ~30 min, and then an excess of pre-cooled ethanol was added to it until yellow coloured microcrystalline $\text{A}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$ compound ceased to appear. The compound was separated by centrifugation, washed four times with cold ethanol and finally dried *in vacuo* over diphosphorous pentoxide. The yield was 85-94%.

Reactions of potassium oxodiperoxovanadate(V), $\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$ with KF, and 2,2'-dipyridyl: To a concentrated aqueous solution of $\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$ was added an aqueous solution of KF, or an ethanolic solution of 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy) with the concentration ratio between $\text{K}[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]$ and KF or dipy

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE VALUES AND STRUCTURALLY SIGNIFICANT IR AND RAMAN BANDS OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Ir band cm^{-1}	Raman band cm^{-1}	Assignments
		A/N	V	O ^a			
NH ₄ [VO(O ₂) ₂]	140	9.2 ^b	34.4	42.5	950 s	945	$\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$
		(9.4) ^b	(34.19)	(42.96)	885 s	880	$\nu_{\text{O}-\text{O}}(\nu_1)$
					605 s	610	$\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}(\nu_2)$
Na[VO(O ₂) ₂]	135	15.3	33.6	41.7	950 s	950	$\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$
		(14.94)	(33.09)	(41.58)	870 s	880	$\nu_{\text{O}-\text{O}}(\nu_1)$
					605 s	600	$\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}(\nu_2)$
K[VO(O ₂) ₂]	130	22.7	30.3	37.2	960 s	945	$\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$
		(23.0)	(29.96)	(37.64)	885 s	875	$\nu_{\text{O}-\text{O}}(\nu_1)$
					605 s	615	$\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}(\nu_2)$
				530 s	525	$\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}(\nu_2)$	

^a Peroxo-oxygen. ^b Analysis for N.

maintained at 1 : 1. The resulting solution was stirred for ~15 min at the ice-bath temperature followed by the addition of cold ethanol until the precipitation of yellow microcrystalline product was complete. It was allowed to stand at the ice-bath temperature for ~30 min, and the product was isolated by centrifugation, purified by washing with ethanol and finally dried *in vacuo* over diphosphorous pentoxide. The product isolated from the reaction of K[VO(O₂)₂] with KF was identified as K₂[VO(O₂)₂F]¹⁹, while that obtained from the reaction of K[VO(O₂)₂] with dipyriddy was found to be K[VO(O₂)₂ dipy].4H₂O¹⁴.

Elemental analyses : Vanadium, peroxide, nitrogen, sodium and potassium were estimated by the methods described earlier²⁰.

The results of elemental analyses, molar conductance values, infrared and Raman band positions along with their assignments are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The yellow alkali metal oxodiperoxovanadates(V), A[VO(O₂)₂] (A=NH₄, Na or K), are soluble in water at ambient temperatures, and they permit conductance measurements. The molar conductances of the newly synthesised compounds were found to lie in the range 130-140 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (Table 1), suggesting 1 : 1 electrolytic nature of each of them in agreement with their formulae. The compounds are all diamagnetic, as evidenced from the results of magnetic susceptibility measurements, in conformity with the view that vanadium occurs in its +5 oxidation state (d⁰) in each of them.

Alkali metal oxodiperoxovanadates(V) can be stored in sealed sample containers and their stability

can be ascertained by the chemical determination of peroxide periodically. The peroxide estimation in such compounds must be considered as very important in order to determine the number of O₂²⁻ group coordinated to the metal centre. The peroxide content was determined by red-ox titrations^{18,20,21} using standard Ce^{IV} solution, and also separately by standard potassium permanganate solution. The titration in each case was carried out in the presence of boric acid in order to prevent any loss of active oxygen, and the results obtained conspicuously suggested the occurrence of two peroxo (O₂²⁻) groups per vanadium atom in each of the compounds.

The infrared and laser Raman spectra of the alkali metal oxodiperoxovanadates(V), A[VO(O₂)₂] (A=NH₄, Na or K), are quite characteristic. Both ir and laser Raman spectra show bands at ~950, ~880, ~610, and ~530 cm^{-1} which have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$ ²², $\nu_{\text{O}-\text{O}}(\nu_1)$ ^{23,24}, $\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}(\nu_2)$ ^{23,24} and $\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}(\nu_2)$ ^{23,24} modes, respectively. The O-O and metal-O₂ bands are important spectroscopic probes for molecular structure determination, and are amenable to infrared and Raman spectroscopic studies. The observed positions of $\nu_{\text{O}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}$ modes, and the number of such vibrations correspond to those which one would expect to observe for a triangularly bonded peroxide ligand^{18,24}, and accordingly it is argued that the peroxide ligands are bonded to the vanadium(V) centre in a triangular bidentate (C_{2v}) manner in each of the newly synthesised compounds. The distinction between ν_2 and ν_3 modes of $\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}$ was made on the basis of the fact that the $\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}$ band at ~530 cm^{-1} was comparatively more sharp and intense than that of the $\nu_{\text{V}-\text{O}_2}$ at ~610 cm^{-1} , and was polarised. The ν_1 mode is well separated from the ν_2 and ν_3 modes and the band at ~880 cm^{-1} is unambiguously

assigned to the ν_1 ($\nu_{\text{O-O}}$) mode of the coordinated peroxide (O_2^{2-}). The strong absorption at $\sim 950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ owes its origin to the presence of a terminally bonded oxygen atom. It is on account of the large polarisability changes involved in the V=O bond that the $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ appears as a strong band in the laser Raman spectra, and is quite characteristic for the newly synthesised compounds. In order to explore the possibility of any change in the structure of the complex anion $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]^-$ in solution, laser Raman spectra of the freshly prepared solutions of alkali metal oxodiperoxovanadates(V) were recorded at ambient temperature. The solution spectra neither showed any new band nor any appreciable change in positions of the peaks observed in the corresponding solid state spectra. The only notable difference was that the solution laser Raman peaks, especially the $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$, $\nu_{\text{O-O}}$ (ν_1) and $\nu_{\text{V-O}_2}$ (ν_2) modes, were found to be relatively sharp. This, therefore, leads us to infer that the complex species $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2)_2]^-$ most probably retains its structural identity both in the solid state as well as in solutions.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a fellowship to one of them (N.S.I.).

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